

Simulation and analysis of MSEPIC Converter Topology for Reducing Torque Ripple of BLDC Motor

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Abstract: Brushless DC (BLDC) motors have been widely used in a number of low- and medium- power applications such as robotics, aerospace, automotive electronics, home appliances, and medical. In BLDC motor, armature current cannot be commutated immediately due to the influence of the armature winding inductance, which leads to the generation of current ripple. The torque ripple due to the current ripple is the main drawback of a BLDC motor that generates speed oscillations, vibrations, and noises. So it is important to reduce the torque ripple in order to ensure smooth operation of BLDC motor. The proposed modified single-ended primary-inductor converter (MSEPIC) topology aims at reducing the torque ripple of a BLDC motor. For torque ripple reduction, the modified SEPIC converter is employed at the entrance of the inverter. The modified SEPIC converter operates with high static gain and less switching voltage stress than classical DC-DC converters. Hence, the modified SEPIC converter is used in this proposed torque ripple suppression circuit and the duty cycle is adjusted to obtain the desired dc-bus voltage based on the spinning speed of the BLDCM. The Simulink models of 2 level inverter-fed BLDC motor, 3 level inverter-fed BLDC motor with modified SEPIC converters and switch selection circuits have been developed using MATLAB software. The analysis and study of the results obtained from these models have been performed to find the effective topology to reduce the torque ripple of the BLDC motor. The analysis has been done at different speeds in order to check the effectiveness of the proposed topology. The suggested dc-bus voltage control strategy is more effective in torque ripple reduction in the commutation interval. In order to obtain significant torque ripple suppression, quietness, and higher efficiency, 3-level inverter with modified SEPIC and the voltage selector circuit is the most suitable.

Keywords: Brushless DC motor, two level inverter, three level inverter, SEPIC converter, torque ripple.

1 Introduction

Brushless DC (BLDC) motors have been widely used in a number of low- and medium- power applications such as robotics, aerospace, automotive electronics, home appliances, and medical. The BLDC motor has several advantages such as high power density, higher inertia to torque ratio, higher efficiency, improved reliability, fast dynamic response, and lesser maintenance. In BLDC motor, armature current cannot be commutated immediately due to the influence of the armature winding inductance, which leads to the generation of current ripple. The torque ripple due to the current ripple is the main drawback of BLDC motor that generates speed oscillations, vibrations, and noises. Several pulse-width modulation (PWM) methods have been proposed over the past few decades to solve this key issue. A new PWM control algorithm has been proposed to eliminate commutation torque ripple by duty ratio control. Special topologies such as a multilevel DC-link converter, buck converter, and SEPIC converter have been proposed by many researchers to reduce the torque ripple of BLDC motor. A multilevel DC-link inverter topology has been proposed for the remarkable torque ripple suppression of BLDC motor with low winding inductance. So, if we can reduce the torque ripples produced in BLDC motor with an efficient topology, it will have a greater importance.

Brushless Direct Current Motor (BLDCM) drives are more popular due to its high power efficiency, high torque to weight and inertia ratios, high power density, high dynamic response, high reliability, compact size and simple control. However, the pulsating torque is one of the key issues in BLDCM.

The BLDCM has a trapezoidal back-EMF waveform, and a stator is fed by quasi square wave line current. Usually, phase winding self-inductance distorts the ideal quasi-square wave line current, which creates the torque ripple [1]. Various hybrid converter topologies have been proposed with a dc-dc converter to improve torque performance of 2-level inverter-fed BLDCM. The commutation torque of a BLDC motor is depending on the commutation transient line current. To calculate the line current accurately, the phase resistance is taken into account, and the phase currents rising and falling speed are compared. Furthermore, it is proved that the line current will maintain constant if the DC voltage is lifted in the commutation period. The desired voltage is even higher than the supplied DC link voltage, if the back EMF is higher than two fifths of the input DC voltage. A super-lift Luo-converter is employed to increase the input voltage [2]. The required waveform of the transient voltage is accomplished by changing the parameters of the power DC/DC converter based on the mathematical modeling for the proposed circuit. A dc-dc single-ended primary inductor converter (SEPIC) and a switch selection circuit are employed in front of the inverter [3]. The desired commutation voltage is accomplished by the SEPIC converter. The dc link voltage control strategy is carried out by the switch selection circuit to separate two procedures, adjusting the SEPIC converter and regulating speed. Simulation and experimental results show that, compared with common dc-dc converter, the SEPIC topology, when applied in a steady state, can reduce commutation torque ripple both at high and low speeds with much faster dc voltage regulation. Modified SEPIC is the new configuration to solve the limitations of classical SEPIC converter [4]. The voltage multiplier technique is applied to the classical SEPIC circuit, obtaining new operation characteristics as low-switch-voltage operation and high static gain at low line voltage. The new configuration also allows the reduction of the losses associated to the diode reverse recovery current, and soft commutation is obtained with a simple regenerative snubber circuit [4]. The components of the converter can be designed according to the requirement and the duty ratio is regulated to get the required dc link voltage according to speed changes of the motor. So a topology based on Modified SEPIC converter is used for reducing commutation torque ripple in BLDCM drives [5]. The reduction

in voltage and current stress of the main switches are the main advantage of this topology.

The brushless DC motors uses power electronic switches for the commutation purpose, it creates the Harmonics in armature current. In order to reduce this harmonics Cascaded H Bridge Multilevel Inverter with current controller can be used, which also reduces the torque ripple produced due to the harmonics induced [6]. A novel topology for reducing commutation torque ripple in a brushless DC motor (BLDCM) drive system using a three-level neutral-point-clamped (NPC) inverter [7] combined with single-ended primary-inductor converter (SEPIC) converters. In the BLDCM, current ripples arise because of the influence of stator winding inductance, which generates torque ripples. The torque ripple that is generated in the commutation period prevents the use of BLDCM in high-precision servo drive systems. In this study, two-stage converters are proposed to reduce the torque ripple. The first stage consists of two SEPIC converters to obtain the desired commutation voltage according to motor speed. A dc-link voltage selection circuit is combined with the SEPIC converters to apply the optimized voltage during the commutation interval. To reduce the torque ripple further, a three-level NPC inverter is used to apply a half dc-link voltage across the motor winding and this effectively reduces the torque ripple. This topology [8] is able to reduce commutation torque ripple significantly under both low-speed and high-speed operation.

In a BLDC motor, armature current cannot be commutated immediately due to the influence of the armature winding inductance, which leads to the generation of current ripple. The BLDCMs have trapezoidal back-EMF waveforms and are fed with rectangular stator currents. However, ideal rectangular current shapes cannot be realized in practice because of the current ripple. The torque ripple primarily affects the accuracy of speed and position control because of the resulting speed ripple, mechanical vibration and unwanted acoustic noise. The torque ripple due to the current ripple is the main drawback of BLDC motor that generates speed oscillations, vibrations, and noises. So developing a topology to mitigate the torque ripple will have greater importance. The main contributions of this work are,

- Designed and implemented an efficient topology for torque ripple reduction in BLDC motor using MSEPIC converter.
- Analyzed the torque ripple at different speeds for two level inverter fed BLDC motor, three level inverter fed BLDC motor, two level inverter fed BLDC motor with MSEPIC and three level inverter fed BLDC motor with Modified SEPIC (MSEPIC).

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed system

2 Materials and Methods

The mathematical modeling of BLDC motor is used to analyze the torque ripples and a modified SEPIC converter topology is used to mitigate this torque ripple. An NPC inverter is used for further reduction in torque ripples through eliminating harmonics. The commutation period of the BLDC motor is identified through developing a logical circuit based on back EMF of the BLDC motor.

A novel converter topology is proposed to reduce the torque ripple of the BLDCM drive system. The proposed converter is composed of a modified SEPIC converter, a 3-level DCMLI, voltage selection circuit and a voltage regulator. The modified SEPIC converter operates with high static gain and less switching voltage stress than classical DC-DC converters. Hence, the modified SEPIC converter is used in this proposed torque ripple suppression circuit and the duty cycle is adjusted to obtain the desired dc-bus voltage based on the spinning speed of the BLDCM. The 3-level DCMLI is used for further reduction of the current ripple and as well as the resultant torque ripple. The MOSFET-based voltage selector circuit is used to apply regulated dc-bus voltage for efficient commutation torque ripple suppression. The block diagram of the proposed converter topology is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 2: Modified SEPIC Converter

Fig. 2 shows the block diagram of the modified single ended primary inductor converter (MSEPIC). The modified single-ended primary-inductor converter (MSEPIC) is a type of DC/DC converter that allows the electrical potential (voltage) at its output to be greater than, less than, or equal to that at its input. The output of the SEPIC is controlled by the duty cycle of the control switch (S). For efficient suppression of torque pulsation, the dc-bus voltage selector circuit is used to apply the regulated dc-bus voltage from the modified SEPIC converter during the commutation interval. A wide range of output voltages can be realized because of the step-up and step-down static gain of MSEPC converter.

Fig. 3 shows the circuit of a neutral point clamped inverter (NPC). An NPC module is often called a three-level module.

When an NPC module is used as in inverter operation, the DC-link voltage can be converted into a variable alternating voltage and variable frequency.

In contrast to a half-bridge or sixpack, an NPC topology offers an additional voltage level at the output. The 3-level inverter promised lower torque ripples and copper losses as compared to the 2-level inverter. A maximum difference of approximately 16.82% and 66.1% lower copper losses and torque ripples respectively were reached at particular switching frequencies and motor speeds.

Fig. 3. NPC inverter

The commutation period of the BLDC motor is identified through developing a logical circuit based on back EMF of the BLDC motor. Theoretically, the BLDC motor produces the trapezoidal back-EMF waveform and the waveform of the excited phase current is quasi square shape. Six-step commutation, also known as trapezoidal commutation, is a commutation technique used to control three-phase BLDC permanent magnet motor. It controls the stator currents to achieve a motor speed and direction of rotation. In the BLDC motor drive, only two of the three-phase windings are excited, while the other winding is left unexcited. This is the difference from the inverter drive method for AC motors.

2.1 System Design

2.1.1. Modified SEPIC Converter design

2.1.1.1 For two level inverter fed BLDC motor

- Switching frequency, $f=5\text{kHz}$
- $V_{IN}=200$
- $V_{OUT}=380$
- $P_{OUT}=518\text{W}$

$$\frac{V_O}{V_{IN}} = \frac{1-D}{1+D}$$

here $D=0.31$

$$I_{IN} = \frac{P_{OUT}}{V_{IN}} = 2.59\text{A}$$

$$I_{OUT} = \frac{P_{OUT}}{V_{OUT}} = 1.363\text{A}$$

Input current ripple, $\Delta I_{IN}=0.29\text{A}$ (10% ripple)

Output voltage ripple, $\Delta V_{OUT}=3.8\text{V}$ (1% ripple)

$$L_1 = \frac{V_{IN}D}{f\Delta I_{IN}} = 47\text{mH}$$

practically L_2 is taken as the half of L_1 , $L_2=23.5\text{mH}$

$$C_S = C_M = \frac{V_{OUT}D}{f\Delta V_{OUT}} = 22\mu\text{F}$$

2.1.1.2 For three level inverter fed BLDC motor

- Switching frequency, $f=5\text{kHz}$
- $V_{IN}=200$
- $V_{OUT}=760$
- $P_{OUT}=518\text{W}$

$$\frac{V_{OUT}}{V_{IN}} = \frac{1-D}{1+D}$$

here $D=0.58$

$$I_{IN} = \frac{P_{OUT}}{V_{IN}} = 2.59\text{A}$$

$$I_{OUT} = \frac{P_{OUT}}{V_{OUT}} = 0.6815\text{A}$$

Input current ripple, $\Delta I_{IN}=0.29\text{A}$ (10% ripple)

Output voltage ripple, $\Delta V_{OUT}=3.8\text{V}$ (1% ripple)

$$L_1 = \frac{V_{IN}D}{f\Delta I_{IN}} = 90\text{mH}$$

practically L_2 is taken as the half of L_1 , therefore $L_2=45\text{mH}$

$$C_S = C_M = \frac{V_{OUT}D}{f\Delta V_{OUT}} = 10.5\mu\text{F}$$

2.1.2.1 Voltage Selector Circuit

Fig. 4. Back Emf and stator current

The voltage selection circuit is used for the insertion of MSEPIC converter during commutation interval. It is important to identify the commutation interval of the BLDC motor for the proper working of this voltage selection circuit. Theoretically, the BLDC motor produces the trapezoidal back-EMF waveform and the waveform of the excited phase current is quasi square shape as shown in Fig. 4. The six commutation intervals in cycle of rotation is represented by S1,S2,S3,S4,S5 and S6. To identify the commutation interval we need to design and implement a logic circuit. For accurate prediction of the commutation interval six inputs are taken from three phases of back emf (A- Ea+ve, B- Eb+ve,C- Ec+ve,D- Ea-ve,E- Eb-ve,F- Ec-ve). The truth table for the required logic circuit is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Truth Table to find commutation interval

A	B	C	D	E	F	Y
1	0	1	0	1	0	1
1	0	0	0	1	1	1
1	1	0	0	0	1	1
0	1	0	1	0	1	1
0	1	1	1	0	0	1
0	0	1	1	1	0	1

The K-map representation of Table 1 is shown in Fig. 5

Fig. 5. K-map representation

The SOP expansion of the designed logic circuit is given by

$$Y = A'B'CDEF + A'BCDE'F + A'BCDE'F + AB'C'D'EF + AB'CD'EF + ABC'D'E'F$$

The logic circuit designed for the voltage selection circuit using above SOP expansion is given Fig.6.

Fig. 6. Logic circuit for voltage selection circuit

The output pulses from the logic circuit is fed to a triggered pulse generator to produce pulses of width equal to commutation interval. The commutation interval can be calculated by the equation given below. Here L is the phase inductance, I_m is the maximum value of stator current, V_{dc} is the input voltage and E_m is the back emf.

$$T_f = \frac{3LI_m}{V_{dc} + 2E_m}$$

2.2 Simulation parameters

The parameters used for simulation are shown in Table 2. Table 3 shows the parameters BLDC motor.

Table 2: MSEPIC converter parameters.

Parameter	Value
Input Voltage	200V
Output Voltage	760V
Output Power	518W
Inductance L_1	90mH
Inductance L_2	45mH
Capacitor C_s	10 μ F
Capacitor C_M	10 μ F

Table 3: parameters for BLDC motor.

Parameter	Value
Voltage, V	200
Rated Power, W	518
Rated Torque, Nm	518
Rated Speed, rad/min	6000
No. of pole pairs	4
Phase Resistance, Ohms	3.1 Ohms
Phase Inductance, mH	3.09 mH
Back-emf Coefficient V/(rad/s)	0.151

3. Results and Discussions

A torque ripple analysis has been conducted and based on this, a novel converter topology is proposed with modified SEPIC converter, which regulates the dc-bus voltage closer to $8E_m$ ($4E_m$ for 2 level inverter) based on the measurement of the rotational speed of BLDCM. The dc-bus voltage selector circuit applies regulated dc-bus voltage during the commutation period, which significantly diminishes the commutation torque ripple.

Fig.7. Modified SEPIC Converter (200V to 760V) output Voltage

The Fig. 7 shows simulated result of the designed MSEPIC converter. The output result shows that the designed MSEPIC converter is able to produce the required output voltage ($8E_m$).

Fig. 8. Modified SEPIC Converter (200V to 380V) output Voltage

The Fig. 8 shows simulated result of the designed MSEPIC converter. The output result shows that the designed MSEPIC converter is able to produce the required output voltage ($4E_m$).

Fig. 9. Stator Current of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 1000RPM

Fig.10. Torque Ripple of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 1000RPM

Fig. 9 shows the stator current of 2 level inverter fed BLDC motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM. Fig.10 shows the obtained torque waveform of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 1000RPM. The percentage torque ripple in the obtained waveform can be calculated from the following equation,

$$\% ripple = \frac{Peak\ to\ peak\ ripple\ value}{Reference\ torque} * 100$$

Here the reference torque value is 0.825 Nm. Therefore

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.3}{0.825} * 100 = 36.36\%$$

The stator current, torque waveform of 2 level inverter fed BLDC motor at 6000 RPM is shown in Fig.11 and Fig.12. The % torque ripple at 6000 Rpm is,

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.45}{0.825} * 100 = 54.8\%$$

Fig. 11. Stator Current of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 6000RPM

Fig.12. Torque Ripple of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 6000RPM

The obtained speed waveforms of 2 Level Inverter fed BLDC motor is shown in Fig.13 and fig.14.

Fig. 13. Speed waveform of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 1000RPM

Fig. 14. Speed waveform of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 6000RPM

The obtained Back emf of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC motor is 22.5V at 1000 RPM and 95V at 6000 RPM as shown in Fig.15 and Fig.16.

Fig .15. Back EMF of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 1000RPM

Fig.16. Back EMF of 2 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 6000RPM

Fig. 17. Stator Current of 3 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 1000RPM

Fig. 18. Torque Ripple of 3 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 1000RPM

The obtained stator current and torque waveforms at 1000 RPM of 3 level inverter fed BLDC motor are shown in Fig. 17 and Fig. 18.

The % torque ripple at 1000 rpm is,

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.23}{0.825} * 100 = 27.8\%$$

The obtained stator current and torque waveforms at 6000 RPM of 3 level inverter fed BLDC motor are shown in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20.

Fig. 19. Stator Current of 3 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 6000RPM

Fig. 20. Torque Ripple of 3 Level inverter fed BLDC Motor at 6000RPM

The % torque ripple at 6000 Rpm is,

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.34}{0.825} * 100 = 41.21\%$$

The obtained stator current waveforms at 1000 RPM of 2 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC is shown in Fig. 21. The enlarged view of DC link voltage for this case is shown in Fig. 22.

Fig. 21. Stator current of two-level inverter fed BLDC motor with MSEPIC at 1000 rpm.

Fig. 22. Enlarged view of DC-link voltage of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM.

Fig. 23. Torque waveform of 2 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM.

The torque waveform of 2 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM is shown in Fig. 23.

The % torque ripple at 1000 RPM is,

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.11}{0.825} * 100 = 13.33\%$$

The obtained stator current waveforms at 6000 RPM of 2 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC is given in Fig. 24. Fig. 25 represents the enlarged view of DC link voltage for this case.

Fig. 24. Stator current at 6000 RPM of 2 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC.

Fig. 25. Enlarged view of DC-link input voltage at 6000 RPM.

Fig. 26. Toque waveform at 6000 RPM.

The obtained torque waveform at 6000 RPM is shown in Fig. 26. The % torque ripple at 1000 RPM is given by the following equation.

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.19}{0.825} * 100 = 23\%$$

Fig. 27. Stator current of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM

Fig. 28. Enlarged view of DC-link voltage of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM.

Fig. 29. Toque waveform at 1000 RPM.

Fig. 27 and Fig. 28 shows the stator current and enlarged view of DC link voltage of 3 level inverter fed BLDC motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM. The torque waveform of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 1000 RPM is shown in Fig. 29.

The % torque ripple at 1000 RPM is,

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.09}{0.825} * 100 = 10.1\%$$

Fig. 30. Stator current of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 6000 RPM

Fig. 31. Enlarged view of DC-link voltage of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 6000 RPM.

Fig. 32. Toque waveform at 6000 RPM.

The input DC link voltage can be regulated according to change in speed of motor using duty ratio control method. The pulses for MSEPIC is controlled produced to get the required output voltage.

The stator current of 3 level inverter fed BLDC motor with MSEPIC at 6000 rpm is shown in Fig. 30. The DC link for this case is shown in Fig. 31. The obtained torque waveform of 3 level inverter fed BLDC motor with MSEPIC at 6000RPM is shown in Fig. 32. The percentage ripple in torque can be calculated as follows,

$$\% ripple = \frac{0.12}{0.825} * 100 = 14.5\%$$

The input DC link voltage can be regulated according to change in speed of motor using duty ratio control method. The pulses for MSEPIC is controlled produced to get the required output voltage. The obtained DC link voltage waveform of 3 level inverter fed BLDC motor at 5000RPM is shown in Fig. 33.

Fig. 33. Enlarged view of DC-link voltage of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 5000 RPM.

The DC link voltage waveform at 4000RPM is shown in Fig.34.

Fig. 34. Enlarged view of DC-link voltage of 3 level Inverter fed BLDC Motor with MSEPIC at 4000 RPM.

Table 2 shows the percentage torque ripple for different topologies. It can be seen that the torque ripple reduces as the level of the inverter increases. It also increases with speed. It can also be observed that the torque ripple has considerably reduced for MSEPIC topology and being the lowest for 3 level inverter with MSEPIC.

Table 2: Percentage Torque ripple for different topologies.

Topology	1000 RPM	6000 RPM
2 level inverter	36.36%	54.8%
3 level inverter	27.8%	41.21%
2 level inverter with MSEPIC	13.33%	23%
3 level inverter with MSEPIC	10.9%	14.54%

4. Conclusions

A commutation torque ripple reduction circuit has been designed and simulated using 3-level DCMLI with modified SEPIC converter and a dc-bus voltage selector circuit in this work. The reduction in voltage and current stress of the main switches are the major advantage of this topology. The suggested dc-bus voltage control strategy is more effective in torque ripple reduction in the commutation interval. The obtained results shows that the modified SEPIC converter and voltage selection circuit is capable of providing desired voltage at the commutation interval. The proposed topology accomplishes the successful reduction of torque ripple in the commutation period and simulation results are presented to compare the performance of the proposed control technique with the conventional 2-level inverter, 3-level DCMLI, 2-level inverter with SEPIC converter and the switch selection circuit fed BLDCM. In order to obtain significant torque ripple suppression, quietness and

higher efficiency, 3-level DCMLI with modified SEPIC converter and the voltage selector circuit is a most suitable choice to obtain high-performance operation of BLDCM.

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